

Analysis of The Value of Humanity in Ahmad Dhani's Song Lyrics : A Critical Discourse Analysis by Mohammad Siddiq

Sofia Deannisa
Aquaculture Production and Management Technology – IPB University
sofiadeannisa@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is to reveal the message of humanity in the lyrics of Ahmad Dhani's song. Ahmad Dhani's song lyrics were analyzed based on three dimensions, namely the textual dimension which includes the linguistic and intertextual aspects of the text, the discursive practice dimension which includes the aspects of text production and consumption, and the social practice dimension, namely by looking at the expression of human values as a form of social action-, and understanding the relationship between them. situational, institutional, and social aspects. The results show that the human values contained in the lyrics of Ahmad Dhani's songs are expressed in the themes of romance, nationalism, socio-political criticism, and religious spirituality. The message of humanity is conveyed in straightforward and metaphorical expressions. In discursive practice, the lyrics of songs with themes of humanity written by Ahmad Dhani still receive facilities from the music industry, which is usually dominated by romance themes. On the other hand, by discussing broader human values through songs with various themes, Ahmad Dhani can widen distribution channels to allow his songs to be accepted more widely.

Keywords: *Human Values, Ahmad Dhani, Lyrics*

INTRODUCTION

In order to more clearly see the importance of research on song lyrics with a critical discourse analysis paradigm, we can consider the effectiveness of using song lyrics as a medium for delivering messages that are not necessarily owned by messages expressed in other forms. The theme, content, and message in the song lyrics are not tied to the type of music, ranging from love issues to socio-political issues. It is also important to note that there are lyrics of popular songs that are proven to have an emancipatory influence socially and promote human values.

In Indonesia, the number of artists who have entered the music industry may be countless. However, of the many artists, only a few consistently voice the idea of humanity through their song lyrics. One of them is Ahmad Dhani, a song lyricist who has a direct or indirect influence on society.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The collected lyrics of Ahmad Dhani's songs were then analyzed based on three dimensions, namely text, discursive practice, and socio-cultural practice. The dimensions of the text (text) are at the micro-level-, so that the analysis of the text is carried out linguistically. The dimension of discourse practices is at the meso level, so this analysis is related to the process of producing and consuming texts. The dimension of socio-cultural practices (sociocultural practices) is at the macro level, so the analysis of this dimension relates to the social context (Fairclough, 2003, pp. 96--98). The technique of checking the validity of the data used in this research is the triangulation technique through multi-analysis (multiple analysis). The results of data analysis are then presented based on these three dimensions as the discussion domain.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are All of Ahmad Dhani's songs can basically be classified into several themes, namely romance, nationalism, environment and nature, spirituality and divinity, social criticism, and social phenomena. It should be noted here that these themes are not absolutely separate. Thematic categories that limit the content of the song are made only as initial limits as a basis for analysis. Because basically, the dominant character of most of Ahmad Dhani's songs is love.

Through understanding some of the song lyrics that have been put forward, although Ahmad Dhani's song lyrics mostly carry the theme of love, they do not entirely express love in the form of a romance story, but there is also a moral message conveyed. The moral message tends to have a religious nuance. In songs with the theme of nationalism, as well as the theme of love, some songs that talk about this theme are related to the issue of nationalism alone, and some are related to other issues, such as important events and social criticism.

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions is As previously discussed, that some of Ahmad Dhani's songs have stronger intertextuality with the lyrics of other songs on the theme of romance than songs with themes, for example, social criticism and nationalism. This

intertextuality, of course, is due to several things. Among them is the theme of romance is a theme which dominates the music industry. Furthermore, it can be said that if you do not have love songs, a musician or songwriter cannot enter the world of the music industry.

From a production point of view, consciously or not, Ahmad Dhani most likely just made a text that is familiar with the problem of love, which could be sourced from another text that often talks about love and is considered an established way. In this way, he created a song text that has a close relationship with other song texts about romance, so that it sounds natural as a love song.

CONCLUSION

How the writer subjectively sees from the paper analysis Based on the discussion that has been done, several things can be concluded. First, on the textual dimension, four main themes can be found in Ahmad Dhani's song, namely romance, nationalism, socio-political criticism, and religious spirituality. Second, on the discursive practice dimension, it can be seen that most of the songs that Ahmad Dhani composed were performed individually. Third, on the dimension of social practice, situationally, there are two kinds of situations that underlie Ahmad Dhani's writing of song lyrics, namely (1) situational events based on his personal experience; (2) the situation of events that are not based on personal experience.

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